

PREDICTING THE DEVELOPMENT OF PREECLAMPSIA IN PREGNANT WOMEN WITH EXCESS BODY WEIGHT AND OBESITY

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Abstract. *Preeclampsia is a specific complication in pregnant women that develops in the second half of pregnancy. It is a common cause of maternal and perinatal mortality. The pathogenesis of preeclampsia is associated with placental ischemia, which develops as a result of improper remodeling and dilation of spiral arteries, stimulating the release of inflammatory mediators and placental factors that cause maternal endothelial dysfunction and hypertension. This process is exacerbated if preeclampsia occurs in the context of obesity, as excess body weight contributes to the development of chronic inflammatory processes, metabolic and endocrine disorders. This article will discuss the mechanisms through which obesity affects the course of pregnancy and the development of preeclampsia, as well as present laboratory research data confirming this connection.*

Keywords: *preeclampsia, triglycerides, cholesterol, LDL (low-density lipoproteins), HDL (high-density lipoproteins), adiponectin, placental insufficiency.*

Introduction. The problem of obesity is a global issue worldwide. According to WHO data for 2022, over 1 billion people were already suffering from obesity, and by 2024, one in eight people is expected to be affected by obesity. Pregnant women suffering from obesity are at high risk of developing a number of complications, such as: post-term pregnancy, fetoplacental insufficiency, fetal hypotrophy or macrosomia, threatened miscarriage, and the development of preeclampsia. [3,7]

Preeclampsia is a multisystem pathological condition that complicates the course of pregnancy, childbirth, and the postpartum period, characterized by arterial hypertension after 20 weeks of pregnancy combined with dysfunction of one or more organs and/or significant proteinuria. Although hypertension and other signs of preeclampsia are often accompanied by newly onset proteinuria or edema, in some women they may manifest in their absence. The incidence of preeclampsia ranges from 2 to 8% per year, and 10-15% of all cases of maternal mortality worldwide are associated with preeclampsia or eclampsia, which amounts to at least 70,000 deaths per year (protocol). The pathogenesis of preeclampsia is still not fully understood, but there are a number of factors that contribute to its manifestation. These include: first pregnancy, multiple pregnancy, obesity, diabetes mellitus, kidney diseases, and others. [6]

Let's consider the physiology of a normally progressing pregnancy. During physiological pregnancy, uterine blood flow increases to ensure placental perfusion and maintain fetal blood supply. The increase in blood flow is achieved through the physiological transformation of the uterine spiral arteries. In this process, trophoblasts penetrate the arterial wall, destroy it, and transform the spiral arteries from narrow-diameter vessels into large-diameter vessels. Thus, in physiological pregnancy, normal placental perfusion is achieved [8].

The pathogenesis of preeclampsia involves a two-stage process. In the first stage, improper placental development occurs when trophoblast cells do not sufficiently penetrate the decidual membrane. This leads to the spiral arteries losing their ability to remodel and expand in diameter. As a result, pregnant women with preeclampsia experience decreased uteroplacental blood flow, and the lack of blood supply to the fetus deprives it of nutrients and oxygen necessary for growth and development. The mechanisms listed above cause placental ischemia, which is a strong stimulus for the release of soluble placental factors into the maternal bloodstream, contributing to the development of the second stage of preeclampsia. These factors associated with placental ischemia include inflammatory cytokines (T-helper-1, T-helper-17 cells), TNF- α , autoantibodies to angiotensin II type 1 receptors (AT1-AA), natural killer cells, reactive oxygen species (superoxide and hydrogen peroxide), and anti-angiogenic factors (soluble FMS-like tyrosine kinase-1 (sFlt-1) and soluble endoglin). Each of these factors causes endothelial dysfunction by reducing the vasodilator nitric oxide (NO) and producing the vasoconstrictor peptide endothelin. In the kidneys, vascular dysfunction leads to changes in renal hemodynamics and a decrease in renal excretory function, manifesting as hypertension and proteinuria [9].

Metabolic factors associated with obesity can increase the risk of preeclampsia by influencing these pathophysiological mechanisms. First, maternal obesity contributes to excessive lipid accumulation in the placenta, leading to impaired trophoblast invasion, angiogenesis, and nutrient transport from mother to fetus, which in turn exacerbates oxidative stress. Secondly, many pro-inflammatory factors, such as tumor necrosis factor (TNF- α) and interleukin (IL) -6, are located in adipose tissue and cause a state of mild systemic inflammation. Thirdly, obesity causes sensitivity, through which placental ischemia factors can create endothelial dysfunction and hypertension [5].

Additionally, adipose tissue hormones play a special role in the development of complications in women with obesity. Adipose tissue produces leptin, resistin, and adiponectin, which affect the course of pregnancy. Let's consider adiponectin as an early marker of preeclampsia development. Adiponectin is a protein consisting of 244 amino acids, secreted predominantly by white adipose tissue. Its level decreases in parallel with increasing obesity, and it has been shown to mediate obesity-induced hypertension. Maternal serum adiponectin levels decrease from the first to the third trimester during normal pregnancy and regulate trophoblast proliferation in the decidual membrane. Furthermore, decreased adiponectin levels can cause hypertension, endothelial dysfunction, inflammation, and proteinuria [1,2].

The mechanisms by which obesity can cause impaired trophoblast migration and, consequently, disruption of uteroplacental blood circulation may be related to metabolic disorders such as hyperlipidemia, hyperinsulinemia, and hypercholesterolemia. These may also serve as markers of preeclampsia onset [4].

Based on these assumptions, we decided to investigate adiponectin levels and lipid profile indicators in pregnant women with preeclampsia and obesity, pregnant women with preeclampsia and normal body mass index, and women without signs of preeclampsia and obesity. This was done to draw conclusions about whether these indicators are the first signs of preeclampsia development in pregnant women.

Materials and methods of research.

A study was conducted on 120 women in their third trimester of pregnancy who were admitted to the Republican Perinatal Center in 2023-2024. The main group consisted of 80 women

with preeclampsia and varying degrees of obesity. The diagnosis of preeclampsia was made based on the criteria of the national clinical guidelines. There were two control groups: Group 1 - women with preeclampsia and normal body weight, and Group 2 - women without excess body weight and with physiological pregnancy. Exclusion criteria included multiple pregnancy and urgent obstetric conditions. Plasma adiponectin levels were determined using an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) with BioVendor (Czech Republic) reagents. The lipid profile (triglycerides, cholesterol, LDL, and HDL) was determined for all pregnant women. Body mass index (BMI) was calculated for each patient using the following formula: $BMI = \text{Weight (kg)} / [\text{Height (m)}]^2$, and patients were divided into corresponding groups according to the WHO classification (Table 1).

Category	BMI (kg/m ²)
Underweight	< 18,5
Normal weight	18,5 – 24,9
Overweight	25,0 – 29,9
Obesity Class I	30,0 – 34,9
Obesity Class II	35,0 – 39,9
Obesity Class III	≥ 40,0

In the main group of pregnant women with excess body weight (22 pregnant women), the average BMI was 26.6 (23.7-29.8), in women with grade I obesity (25) the BMI was 33.3 (31.1-34.7), in women with grade II obesity (20) the average BMI was 37.1 (34.1-39.0), and in women with grade III obesity (13) the BMI was 42.8 (40.1-48). The mean BMI in the group of pregnant women with preeclampsia and normal weight (control group 1) was 23.5 (20.8-24.9). In the 2nd control group of pregnant women without preeclampsia and with normal weight, the average BMI was 23.2 (19.5-24.9).

Results: It was established that the adiponectin level in the main group of pregnant women with preeclampsia and excess weight (n=22) averaged 16.4 (14.0-19.2), with grade I obesity (n=25) - 13.3 (4.21-19.2), with grade II obesity (n=20) - 6.8 (3.1-19.8), and with grade III obesity (n=13) - 2.7 (2.1-4.1). In pregnant women with preeclampsia and normal body weight (Control group 1) (n=20), the adiponectin level was 14.87, while in women with normal pregnancy and normal body weight (control group 2) (n=20), the adiponectin level was 16.9. The data is presented in Diagram 1.

Lipid spectrum levels in the main group of pregnant women with overweight (n=22) were: triglycerides - 2.84, cholesterol - 6.03, HDL - 1.12, and LDL - 3.71. In pregnant women with grade I obesity (n=25): triglycerides - 3.03, cholesterol - 6.63, HDL - 0.97, and LDL - 3.87. Pregnant women with grade II obesity (n=20): triglycerides - 3.3, cholesterol - 7.38, HDL - 0.83, and LDL - 4.5. In pregnant women with grade III obesity (n=13): triglycerides - 4.19, cholesterol - 8.36, HDL - 0.69, and LDL - 4.8. In the 1st control group (pregnant women with preeclampsia and normal body weight) (n=20): triglycerides - 2.02, cholesterol - 5.56, HDL - 1.15, and LDL - 3.12. In the 2nd control group (women with physiologically normal pregnancy and normal body weight) (n=20): triglycerides - 1.96, cholesterol - 5.88, HDL - 1.15, and LDL - 3.48. The results are presented in Diagram 2.

Conclusions:

The obtained results indicate that obesity in pregnant women is a significant risk factor for preeclampsia and is associated with pronounced metabolic and hormonal disorders. The decrease in adiponectin levels and changes in lipid profile, including increased triglycerides, cholesterol, and LDL while simultaneously reducing HDL, are exacerbated with increasing degrees of obesity and play a key role in the pathophysiology of preeclampsia. These changes contribute to impaired placental blood circulation, systemic inflammation, and endothelial dysfunction, leading to a high risk of pregnancy complications such as placental insufficiency, fetal growth restriction or macrosomia, and the threat of preterm labor. The data underscore the need for early detection and monitoring of metabolic changes in pregnant women with obesity for timely prevention and treatment of preeclampsia, taking into account individual characteristics.

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